

Exploring the Relationship Existing between Innovative Activities and the Economic Growth of Ghana

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Abstract: Growth rate is low in major developing countries. *Is it because such countries have not embraced innovation in their development agenda?* The paper explores the relationship existing between innovation and economic growth in Ghana. It moves further to investigate whether or not there has been any impact on economic development. Through a qualitative empirical study, the researchers examine data from the world development indicators, World Bank and the bank of Ghana for the period 2009 to 2019. The researchers observed that, in the short run, an increase in wage bill (expenditure on innovation) led to an increase in the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Further increases in wage bill led to declining GDP. This shows that increasing expenditure on innovation does not necessarily lead to an increase in GDP, but rather the, quality of innovative activities rather positively impacts the country's GDP

Keywords: Innovation, Economic Growth, Economic Development ,Gross Domestic Product, Wage Bill

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Introduction

Ghana is a West African country that share borders with Togo to the East, Ivory Coast to the West, Burkina Faso to the North and the South facing the Atlantic Ocean. With a population of over thirty million people, the country has rich mineral resources such as gold, diamond, silver, arable land for farming and oil deposit.

However, the level of economic development does not reflect the strength of her riches. This is reflected in the serious economic challenges facing the country. Most especially a portion of the youth engage in illegal mining that destroys water bodies and aquatic lives. According to the youth, there are no jobs due to over dependence on public sector jobs. Because a chunk of the youth especially, the graduates, seek employment with the government contributing to huge public sector expenditure.

The writers strongly agree with Barro (1991) that, there is a negative effect on economic growth when there is high rate of government spending. The most pathetic period is the electioneering year. Most developing countries exceed their budgets and over spend which goes a long way to affect the preceding year.

To be able to improve her economic growth and development, Ghana needs to inculcate the spirit of entrepreneurship in the youth. This can be achieved through human capital development, efficient and quality innovative activities. It is said that the youth is the future of a country. Equipping the youth with the right skills, technical abilities, entrepreneurial mindset and assistance, they will become valuable assets to the country. Entrepreneurship is seemingly related to innovation in the business and economics arena. The entrepreneur either adds value to already existing resources or employs the effective and efficient methods to generate value for resources. As Russel S. Sobel put it in econlib.com, when the market value generated by this new combination of resources is greater than the market value these resources can generate elsewhere individually or in some other combination, the entrepreneur makes profit. Improving human capital is the surest way by which the young population in Ghana will be able to take up entrepreneurship as the way forward.

Since economic growth basically entails quantitative measures, this paper uses Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth rate as the measure of economic growth, and the country's Wage Bill which sums up the total expenditure on innovation including human capital development through R&Ds. This paper is organized into two main parts; the relationship existing between innovation and economic growth, and the impact of the relationship on the country's economic growth. This will be followed by the summary and conclusion as well as recommendations to policy makers of the Ghanaian economy.

Economic Growth and Development

Economic growth is an increase in an economy's ability to produce goods and services relative to the baseline or past periods (Lewis, 2013).

Economic Growth and development are two different areas of economic analysis; however, some writers sometimes tend to use them interchangeably. This paper sticks to the norm by stating that Economic Growth deals with the expansion of a country's capacity to produce goods and services within a certain time period to satisfy the populace. It is basically a quantitative measure of what is produced in an economy using such parameters as Gross Domestic Product and Gross National Product to help measure the entire economy.

Economic Development on the other hand goes beyond quantitative measurement to include socioeconomic factors such as the living standard of the populace through the improvement of certain factors as in human capital, technology and how the economy interacts with the society especially how social institutions are managed properly.

Innovation

Innovation refers to the application of improved and efficient ways of undertaking an economic activity within a country.

Theglobaleconomy.com has presented innovation index based on the World Bank Groups publications. Ideally, in their quest to get figures for innovation, researchers focus on expenses of research and development (R&D), information technology expense related, high technology manufacturing and exports, and expenses related to patents. However, available information on such indexes are very scanty and have variations in the dates they were presented, which makes it very difficult to get accurate figures for the years understudy. Most importantly as innovation is considered a new field of research for Ghana, data available just span for less than a decade.

Measures of Innovation.

Institutions and researchers still have different ways of measuring innovation to its fullest. For example, Galway City and County Council Industry and Economic Baseline Study on Innovation Measurement White Paper focus on innovation measures and indicators at two levels; (a) macro measures of innovation that are used for international comparisons and compiled by national statistical agencies, and, (b) measures of innovation and indicators on firm levels. They further stated that measuring innovation is a complex and difficult task. However, they managed to present breakdowns of the measurement of innovation into generational views shown in a table credited to Centre for Accelerating Innovation, George Washington University (2006),

First Generation Input Indicators (1950s–60s)	Second Generation Output Indicators (1970s–80s)	Third Generation Innovation Indicators (1990s)	Fourth Generation Process Indicators (2000s plus emerging focus)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R&D expenditures • S&T personnel • Capital • Tech intensity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patents • Publications • Products • Quality change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation surveys • Indexing • Benchmarking innovation capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge • Intangibles • Networks • Demand • Clusters • Management techniques • Risk/return • System dynamics

Source: Centre for Accelerating Innovation, George Washington University (2006)

Table 1: Innovation indicators timeline

We can see from the presentation that innovation is understood and measured differently by different generations. Theglobaleconomic.com has further captured elements of global innovation index to include such elements of national economies that enable innovative activities such as institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication and business sophistication.

They specifically singled out two output elements and the pillars that capture actual evidence of innovation outputs as *Knowledge and Technology outputs* and *Creative outputs*. Therefore Ghana's innovation index is based on these elements from as early as 2011 to 2019, with figures and years shown in figure 1;

Figure 1: Ghana’s Innovation Index from 2011 to 2019

Source: https://www.theglobaleconomy.com/Ghana/GII_Index/

It can be seen from the above that, the average value for Ghana during the period was 28.44 points with a minimum of 24.50 points in 2018, and a maximum of 32.50 points in 2011, with 25.30 points being the latest value for 2019. Theglobaleconomy.com further made a comparison for the world average in 2019 based on 129 countries and it stands at 36.31. Out of the 129 countries, Ghana ranked 106 with 25.30. Meanwhile the highest point was 62.70 points in Switzerland, and the lowest point was in Yemen at 14.50. So, this gives a clear view as to the position Ghana stand in terms of global innovation.

Ghana's Innovation index breakdowns 2009-2018.

Ideally, researchers of innovation focus on expenses of R&D figures, expenses on the manufacture of high technology products sometimes called smart products such as aerospace, computers, pharmaceuticals, scientific instruments and electrical machinery. Further research into the specifics of the innovation index revealed that for the period 2009 to 2018, only 2010 data on R&D was recorded at 0.38 percent of GDP. More so, the researchers found it difficult laying hands on some data on certain variables, however, the available date have been presented in the table below:

Year	R&D Expen. (%of GDP)	ICT Exports (%total exports)	High Tech Exports (%of manuf. exports)	High Tech Exports (USD'm)	Patent applications by residents
2018	0.00	0.00	8.26	50.01	13
2017	0.00	0.02	4.44	41.53	15
2016	0.00	0.09	2.29	21.45	14
2015	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	00
2014	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	00

2013	0.00	0.19	5.11	62.42	00
2012	0.00	0.06	7.78	76.34	00
2011	0.00	0.05	1.70	23.76	00
2010	0.38	0.02	2.40	9.25	00
2009	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	00

Table 2: Ghana's Innovation index breakdowns 2009-2018

Source: Theglobaleconomy.com

Credit: The World Bank Group

Table 2 gives a complicated relationship among the various variables used to measure innovation due the fact that some data were unavailable.

This gives the major limitations to the study of Ghana's innovation study, therefore, a further detailed research work on Ghana's innovation index is needed. For innovation to take place there should be the existing building blocks. As shown above, all of these (institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market and business sophistication, knowledge and technology outputs as well as creative outputs) come together to determine the innovation level of an economy. Traditionally, the most important explanatory factor on innovation is R&D spending because it is believed that R&D is the input in producing innovation, Xiuli and Haizheng (2020), this idea is expressed through the knowledge production function by Griliches (1979), and many studies from Pakes and Griliches, (1984), Hall, Griliches and Hausman, (1986), Hall and Ziedonis (2001). Those studies are deficient because such studies simply regard R&D as the most important input of innovation without going deeper into the details of R&D by showing the mechanisms of R&D that in affect innovation. Xiuli and Haizheng (2020) opines that, Griliches (1979) and others failed to take the firm's resources, mainly general human capital as well as non-R&D innovation into consideration. This paper expand such earlier works to include the contributions from human capital and non-R&D innovation to make innovation a whole, as has been partially explained by theglobaleconomy.com.

Based on the researchers stance that, for innovation to be whole, the building blocks, basically of non-R&D innovation such as reverse engineering, minor modification of products and processes, Kim and Nelson (2000), innovation process of adaptation and learning by doing, Hansen and Serin (1997), and combining existing knowledge in completely new ways, Grimpe and Sofka (2009), undertaken by managers, engineers, staff and even cleaners (without whom there would not be a clean and conducive environment to work), as well as the stability of businesses and society, all come together to ensure there is the creation of a new product, in this case, innovation.

Looking at the complications in getting accurate figures to define business and societal stability, knowledge, technology and creative outputs, the researchers stand on the *ceteris paribus* assumption to base Ghana's expenditure on innovation on the country's *wage bill rates* for the years understudy. It is worth noting that adopting the wage bill comes with a limitation that the private sector and NGOs' expenditure on innovation are cut off but the reasons given below gives justification for such a stand.

1. The country's wage bill (compensation of employees) cover public sector wages, salaries, allowances and deferred wages.
2. Also, since the research design is based on ex-post facto research, having existing data is the foundation of such a research work, and the adopting wage bill which has less complications and most data available is in the right direction.

3. The wage bill rate is large enough to cover all aspects of the government expenditure on the economy which contributes to making innovation possible in the country.

As Xiuli and Haizheng (2020) postulated that a successful innovation may include the participation of firm's other human capital as playing a complementary role towards achieving innovation, the *ceteris paribus* assumption cannot hold for years that witnessed global pandemics like Ebola, SARS, and the on-going Covid-19, etc. Future research will study the effects of the pandemics on the innovation levels and economic growth in such years.

A. Economic Growth and Innovation Relationship

To know the exact relationship existing between Ghana's economic growth and the country's innovation activities, the writers juxtaposed the economic growth pattern with that of the government's expenditure on innovation for the period understudy.

As has already been stated, a country's economic growth means the expansion of a country's capacity to produce goods and services within a certain period for the satisfaction of its people, while innovation refers to the application of improved and efficient ways of undertaking an economic activity within a country. Based on these two definitions, one can easily identify the relationship that should exist between these two important economic variables. In the quest to having economic growth, one cannot rule out the role of innovation. Ghana's economic growth pattern is no different from that of other countries of the world since it varies year by year, increasing and decreasing based on certain domestic factors and external shocks.

According to the World Bank Publication of Ghana's Public Expenditure Review (2017), Ghana's public sector wage bill has grown rapidly since 2010 and now the largest component of public spending. The wage bill rose from 6.9 percent of GDP in 2009 to 11.4 percent in 2012, and then fell to 7.9 percent in 2015, as shown in the table below

	2004- 2009 Average	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016*
Wage Bill								
% of Total Government Revenue	20.6	38.5	42.1	59.9	54.2	46.1	42.2	37.1
% of GDP	4.9	6.7	8	11.4	9.3	8.4	7.9	7.2
Wages & Salaries		6.9	7.6	8.9	8.9	8.3	7.6	7.2
Allowances		0.5	0.9	1.8	1.6	1.6	1.4	1.6
Deferred wages		0.0	0.6	2.5	0.9	0.5	0.6	0.3
Public Sector Employment								
Total (000s)	358	419	450	480	656	640	654	641
Ministries & Departments	358	419	450	480	510	497	520	507
Subverted Agencies					146	143	134	134
% of Labor Force		5.4	5.6	5.8	5.9	5.6	5.7	
% of Population	1.5	1.8	1.9	1.9	2.6	2.4	2.4	

Note: Data are from October 2016

Source: Ghana Ministry of Finance

Table 3: The Public Sector Wage Bill and Workforce, 2008-2016

Credit: World Bank Group 2017

It can therefore be seen that this huge expenditure on public sector within the years captured should yield a substantial amount of returns to the country.

As it can be seen from the table, that the average wage bill recorded between 2004 and 2009 was 4.9 percent, and the average GDP growth of the same period was 6.04 percent showing a positive average signal.

Year	GDP Growth (%)	Annual Change
2018	6.26%	-1.88%
2017	8.14%	4.70%
2016	3.45%	1.27%
2015	2.18%	-0.72%
2014	2.90%	-4.42%
2013	7.31%	-1.98%
2012	9.29%	-4.75%
2011	14.05%	6.15%
2010	7.90%	3.06%
2009	4.84%	-4.31%

Table 4: Ghana GDP Growth Rate - Historical Data

Source: <https://www.macrotrends.net/countries/GHA/ghana/economic-growth-rate>

Credit : The World Bank

Per yearly comparisons of tables 3 and 4 above, the year 2010 recorded 6.7 percent of wage bill while the country's GDP growth rate was 7.90 percent, again an increase in returns. The country's wage bill expenditure to GDP in 2011 was 8 percent while GDP growth rate for the same year was 14.05 percent, also an increase. The year 2012 saw wage bill expenditure at 11.4 percent however, GDP growth was 9.29 percent indicating a fall in returns. Furthermore, the year 2013 recorded a wage bill rate of 9.3 percent but GDP growth was 7.31, again a decrease in returns. The year 2014 recorded 8.4 percent wage bill per GDP while GDP growth rate was 2.90, a further decrease in returns. 2015 had a wage bill rate of 7.9 percent of GDP but GDP growth rate was 2.18 percent, also a decrease in returns. The year 2016 recorded 7.2 percent of wage bill to GDP while the country's GDP growth rate for the same year was 3.5 which also gave a decrease in returns.

According to the Ghana Financial Market, the wage bill rate for 2017 was 7 percent. So compared to table 4, the GDP growth rate of the country was 8.14 percent, seeing a positive return after years of recording decreases. The year 2018 saw a wage bill of 7.7 percent, a 10 percent increase in the previous rate. However, GDP growth rate for 2018 was 6.26 percent representing a decrease in returns to the country, YEN.COM

Table 5 below shows the two tables together for easy understanding.

Year	Wage Bill Expenditure (%of GDP)	GDP Growth Rate
2018	7.7	6.26
2017	7	8.14
2016	7.2	3.5
2015	7.9	2.18
2014	8.4	2.90
2013	9.3	7.31
2012	11.4	9.29
2011	8	14.05
2010	6.7	7.9
2009		4.84

Table 5: Government Expenditures on Wage Bill and GDP Growth

Source: Researcher's analysis

From the above table, we can see that expenditure on wage bill increased from 2009 to 2011, GDP growth rate also increased in the years. In 2012 as wage bill expenditure continued to increase to 11.4 percent, GDP growth rate started to decline to 9.29 percent. As expenditure on wage bill started to decline from 2013 to 2017, GDP growth also declined from 2012 to 2016, exhibiting a positive relationship between them. However, in the year 2017 as wage bill stood at 7 percent, GDP moved upwards to 8.14 percent but fell to 6.26 percent the following year while wage bill increased to 7.7 percent.

A. The Impacts of innovation on economic growth

From the analysis in table 5, one can clearly see that, in the short run, an increase in wage bill (expenditure on innovation) led to an increase in the country's GDP. A further increase in wage bill led to declining GDP. This shows that increasing expenditure on innovation does not necessarily lead to an increase in GDP. This is in line with Barro (1991), that, there is a negative effect on economic growth when there is high rate of government spending. Although this wage bill expenditure has been used to represent the entire expenditure on innovation, it cannot represent a total government

expenditure in the economy. However, in terms of the comparison between the country's economic development and innovation (wage bill expenditure) it is important to re-emphasize that, huge expenditure on innovation does not guarantee a growing economy. But the quality of the innovative activities would inevitably cushion the economy towards economic growth and development.

Summary and Conclusion

To sum up, for Ghana to achieve a high level economic growth and development, the country must ensure to invest in quality innovative activities and also cut down on excessive spending on some areas of the Ghanaian economy which bloats government expenditure, since having a huge expenditure does not guarantee positive economic growth and development. For the country to be able to improve her economic growth and development, there is the need for the country to inculcate entrepreneurship spirit in the youth through human capital development, and blend quality innovative activities, coupled with reasonable government expenditure, with economic growth agenda.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend to governments, NGOs, opinion leaders and civil society to fully accept innovation in their fields of endeavor but be mindful of not overspending on innovation. In furtherance of this, government agencies in particular must scrutinize every innovative activity that the various departments embark on to screen-out the non-viable ones in order to cut down on expenditure. More so, the government agencies should be equipped in data gathering, especially on innovation activities, expenditure, returns, and a complete agency or department needs to be established to handle Ghana's innovative activities since innovation is the way to the future. Finally, the Youth must be encouraged to embrace innovation and entrepreneurship so that they will not be dependent on the government for public sector jobs. This will help expand the private sector and at the same time help to reduce public wage bill expenditure.

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